

Spain | One Health Surveillance | West Nile fever

Background & objectives

The objective was to improve integrated West Nile fever (WNF) surveillance in Andalusia by:

- Integrating information using a One Health framework
- Implementing entomological surveillance
- Inclusion of additional stakeholders
- Reducing reporting time between stakeholders
- Improving communication with citizens and professionals through practical documents

Outcomes & Impact

- Development of a Strategic Plan for the Surveillance and Control of Arthropod Vectors, which can be found [here](#)
- Launch of the updated integrated vector control and surveillance program for WNF, which can be found [here](#)
- Improvements to the surveillance system of human WNF, including sequencing of isolates, and strengthening coordination mechanisms with local administrations
- Risk of WNF is now categorized using a simplified risk coefficient

Lessons learned

- Integrated surveillance of WNF in humans, animals (e.g. arthropods, equines and wild birds), facilitated the detection of West Nile virus in previously unaffected areas, as well as the detection of a lineage detected for the first time in Andalusia
- Integrated surveillance of WNF provides information for the early adoption of public health control measures
- End-of-season reports enabled the refinement of protocols, control and surveillance plans

Core messages

- Establishing One Health surveillance for WNF enables more timely detection of viral spread
- Integrated surveillance facilitates collaboration between relevant stakeholder from both public and private sectors
- It is necessary to develop tools for predicting vector activity and virus circulation based on environmental and animal data